

The indefinite symbolic plithogenic trigonometric integrals

Yaser Ahmad Alhasan^{1*}, Suliman Sheen², Raja Abdullah Abdulfatah³ and Mohammed Mustafa Ahmed⁴

^{1*}Deanship of the Preparatory Year, Prince Sattam bin Abdulaziz University, KSA; y.alhasan@psau.edu.sa

⁴Deanship the Preparatory Year, Prince Sattam bin Abdulaziz University, Alkharj, Saudi Arabia.; S.salmleh@psau.edu.sa

³Deanship the Preparatory Year, Prince Sattam bin Abdulaziz University, Alkharj, Saudi Arabia.; r.abdulfatah@psau.edu.sa

⁴Department of mathematics, Faculty of science, Islamic University of Madinah, Madinah 42351, Saudi Arabia;
mohamemedm086@gmail.com

*Corresponding author: y.alhasan@psau.edu.sa

Abstract: This paper discussed the indefinite plithogenic trigonometric integrals, where we presented the integrating products of plithogenic trigonometric function, also studying the plithogenic trigonometric identities, which facilitated finding the integral of the associated formulas. In addition to a set of exercises that clarify each idea.

Keywords: trigonometric integrals; plithogenic trigonometric function; plithogenic trigonometric identities.

1. Introduction and Preliminaries

To The genesis, origination, formation, development, and evolution of new entities through dynamics of contradictory and/or neutral and/or noncontradictory multiple old entities is known as plithogenic. Plithogeny advocates for the integration of theories from several fields.

We use numerous "knowledges" from domains like soft sciences, hard sciences, arts and literature theories, etc. as "entities" in this study, this is what Smarandache introduced, as he presented a study on plithogeny, plithogenic set, logic, probability, and statistics [2], in addition to presenting introduction to the symbolic plithogenic algebraic structures (revisited), through which he discussed several ideas, including mathematical operations on plithogenic numbers [1]. Also, an overview of plithogenic set and symbolic plithogenic algebraic structures was discussed by him [3]. It is thought that the symbolic n-plithogenic sets are a good place to start when developing algebraic extensions for other classical structures including rings, vector spaces, modules, and equations [4-5-6-7].

Paper is divided into four parts. Provides an introduction in the first portion, which includes a review of Plithogenic science. A few definitions of a Plithogenic and operations with plithogenic numbers are covered in the second section. The third section defined plithogenic functions. The paper's conclusion is provided in the fourth section.

Alhasan also presented several papers on calculus, in which he discussed neutrosophic definite and indefinite integrals. He also presented the most important applications of definite integrals in neutrosophic logic [8-9]. Alhasan, Smarandache and Abdulfatah presented the indefinite symbolic plithogenic integrals [10].

Division of Symbolic Plithogenic Numbers [1]

Let consider two symbolic plithogenic numbers as below:

$$PN_r = a_0 + a_1P_1 + a_2P_2 + \dots + a_rP_r$$

$$PN_s = b_0 + b_1P_1 + b_2P_2 + \dots + b_sP_s$$

$$\frac{PN_r}{PN_s} = \begin{cases} \text{none, one many} & r \geq s \\ \emptyset & r < s \end{cases}$$

This paper covered a number of topics; the indefinite plithogenic trigonometric integrals were covered in the main discussion section after the introduction and preliminary information were presented in the first section. The paper's conclusion is provided in the final section.

Main Discussion

We will consider C the constant of the symbolic plithogenic integral defined as:

$$C = a_0 + a_1P_1 + a_2P_2 + \dots + a_nP_n, \text{ where: } a_0, a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n \text{ are real numbers.}$$

Integrating products of symbolic plithogenic trigonometric function:

I. $\int PN_r \sin^m(PN_s x) \cos^n(PN_s x) dx$, where m and n are positive integers.

To find this integral, we can distinguish the following two cases:

- Case n is odd:
 - split of $\cos(PN_s x)$
 - apply $\cos^2(PN_s x) = 1 - \sin^2(PN_s x)$
 - we substitution $u = \sin(PN_s x)$
- Case m is odd:
 - split of $\sin(PN_s x)$
 - apply $\sin^2(PN_s x) = 1 - \cos^2(PN_s x)$
 - we substitution $u = \cos(PN_s x)$

Example 1

Find: $\int (P_3 + 1) \sin^2(P_2 + 2)x \cos^3(P_2 + 2)x dx$

Solution:

$$\begin{aligned} \int (P_3 + 2) \sin^2(P_3 + 1)x \cos^3(P_3 + 1)x dx &= \int (P_3 + 2) \sin^2(P_3 + 1)x \cos^2(P_3 + 1)x \cos(P_3 + 1)x dx \\ &= \int (P_3 + 2) \sin^2(P_3 + 1)x (1 - \sin^2(P_3 + 1)x) \cos(P_3 + 1)x dx \\ &= \int [(P_3 + 2) \sin^2(P_3 + 1)x - (P_3 + 2) \sin^4(P_3 + 1)x] \cos(P_3 + 1)x dx \end{aligned}$$

By substitution:

$$u = \sin(P_3 + 1)x \quad \Rightarrow \quad du = (P_3 + 1) \cos(P_3 + 1)x dx$$

$$\Rightarrow \quad = \int \left[\left(\frac{P_3 + 2}{P_3 + 1} \right) u^2 - \left(\frac{P_3 + 2}{P_3 + 1} \right) u^4 \right] du$$

$$= \left(\frac{P_3 + 2}{P_3 + 1} \right) \left(\frac{u^3}{3} - \frac{u^5}{5} \right) + C = \left(2 - \frac{1}{2} P_3 \right) \left(\frac{\sin^3(P_3 + 1)x}{3} - \frac{\sin^5(P_3 + 1)x}{5} \right) + C$$

where:

$C = a_0 + a_1 P_1 + a_2 P_2 + a_3 P_3$; a_0, a_1, a_2, a_3 are real numbers.

and:

$$\frac{P_3 + 2}{P_3 + 1} = x_0 + x_1 P_1 + x_2 P_2 + x_3 P_3$$

$$P_3 + 2 = (P_2 + 1)(x_0 + x_1 P_1 + x_2 P_2 + x_3 P_3)$$

$$P_3 + 2 = x_0 P_3 + x_1 P_3 + x_2 P_3 + x_3 P_3 + x_0 + x_1 P_1 + x_2 P_2 + x_3 P_3$$

$$P_3 + 2 = x_0 + x_1 P_1 + x_2 P_2 + (x_0 + x_1 + x_2 + 2x_3) P_3, \text{ then:}$$

$$x_0 = 2, x_1 = 0, x_2 = 0, x_3 = -\frac{1}{2}$$

hence: $\frac{P_3+2}{P_3+1} = 2 - \frac{1}{2} P_3$

let's check the answer:

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{d}{dx} \left[\left(2 - \frac{1}{2} P_3 \right) \left(\frac{\sin^3(P_3 + 1)x}{3} - \frac{\sin^5(P_3 + 1)x}{5} \right) + C \right] \\ &= \left(2 - \frac{1}{2} P_3 \right) \left(\frac{3(P_3 + 1) \sin^2(P_3 + 1)x \cdot \cos(P_3 + 1)x}{3} - \frac{5(P_3 + 1) \sin^4(P_3 + 1)x \cdot \cos(P_3 + 1)x}{5} \right) \\ &= \left(2 - \frac{1}{2} P_3 \right) (P_3 + 1) \sin^2(P_3 + 1)x (1 - \sin^2(P_3 + 1)x) \cos(P_3 + 1) \\ &= (P_3 + 2) \sin^2(P_3 + 1)x \cos^2(P_3 + 1)x \cos(P_3 + 1) \\ &= (P_3 + 2) \sin^2(P_3 + 1)x \cos^3(P_3 + 1)x \quad (\text{The same integral function}) \end{aligned}$$

II. $\int \tan^m(PN_s x) \sec^n(PN_s x) dx$, where m and n are positive integers.

To find this integral, we can distinguish the following cases:

➤ Case n is even:

- split of $\sec^2(PN_s x)$
- apply $\sec^2(PN_s x) = 1 + \tan^2(PN_s x)$
- we substitution $u = \tan(PN_s x)$

➤ Case m is odd:

- split of $\sec(PN_s x) \tan(PN_s x)$
- apply $\tan^2(PN_s x) = \sec^2(PN_s x) - 1$

- we substitution $u = \sec(PN_s x)$

➤ Case m even and n odd:

- apply $\tan^2(PN_s x) = \sec^2(PN_s x) - 1$
- we substitution $u = \sec(PN_s x)$ or $u = \tan(PN_s x)$, depending on the case.

Example 2

$$\text{Find: } \int (-3P_7 + 4P_6) \tan^2(P_6 x) \sec^4(P_6 x) dx$$

Solution:

$$n = 4 \text{ (even)}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \int (-3P_7 + 4P_6) \tan^2(P_6 x) \sec^4(P_6 x) dx &= \int (-3P_7 + 4P_6) \tan^2(P_6 x) \sec^2(P_6 x) \sec^2(P_6 x) dx \\ &= \int (-3P_7 + 4P_6) (\tan^2(P_6 x) + \tan^4(P_6 x)) \sec^2(P_6 x) dx \end{aligned}$$

by substitution:

$$u = \tan(P_6 x) \quad \Rightarrow \quad du = P_6 \sec^2(P_6 x) dx$$

$$\Rightarrow \int (-3P_7 + 4P_6) (\tan^2(P_6 x) + \tan^4(P_6 x)) \sec^2(P_6 x) dx$$

$$= \frac{-3P_7 + 4P_6}{P_6} \int (u^2 + u^4) du$$

$$= (x_0 + x_1 P_1 + x_2 P_2 + x_3 P_3 + x_4 P_4 + x_5 P_5 + x_6 P_6 - 3P_7) \left(\frac{u^3}{3} + \frac{u^5}{5} \right) + C$$

$$= (x_0 + x_1 P_1 + x_2 P_2 + x_3 P_3 + x_4 P_4 + x_5 P_5 + x_6 P_6 - 3P_7) \left(\frac{\tan^3(P_6 x)}{3} + \frac{\tan^5(P_6 x)}{5} \right) + C$$

where:

$C = a_0 + a_1 P_1 + a_2 P_2 + a_3 P_3 + a_4 P_4 + a_5 P_5 + a_6 P_6 + a_7 P_7$; $a_0, a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4, a_5, a_6, a_7$ are real numbers.

and:

$$\frac{-3P_7 + 4P_6}{P_6} = x_0 + x_1 P_1 + x_2 P_2 + x_3 P_3 + x_4 P_4 + x_5 P_5 + x_6 P_6 + x_7 P_7$$

$$-3P_7 + 4P_6 = (P_6 x) (x_0 + x_1 P_1 + x_2 P_2 + x_3 P_3 + x_4 P_4 + x_5 P_5 + x_6 P_6 + x_7 P_7)$$

$$-3P_7 + 4P_6 = x_0 P_6 + x_1 P_6 + x_2 P_6 + x_3 P_6 + x_4 P_6 + x_5 P_6 + x_6 P_6 + x_7 P_7$$

$$-3P_7 + 4P_6 = (x_0 + x_1 + x_2 + x_3 + x_4 + x_5 + x_6) P_6 + x_7 P_7$$

then:

$$x_0 + x_1 + x_2 + x_3 + x_4 + x_5 + x_6 = 4 \text{ and } x_7 = -3$$

hence:

$$\frac{-3P_7+4P_6}{P_6} = x_0 + x_1P_1 + x_2P_2 + x_3P_3 + x_4P_4 + x_5P_5 + x_6P_6 - 3P_7$$

where: $x_0 + x_1 + x_2 + x_3 + x_4 + x_5 + x_6 = 4$

Example 3

Find:

$$\int (P_4 - 3) \tan^3(P_1 + 1)x \sec^3(P_1 + 1)x \, dx$$

Solution:

$m = 3$ (odd)

$$\begin{aligned} & \int (P_4 - 3) \tan^3(P_1 + 1)x \sec^3(P_1 + 1)x \, dx \\ &= \int (P_4 - 3) \tan^2(P_1 + 1)x \sec^2(P_1 + 1)x \sec(P_1 + 1)x \tan(P_1 + 1)x \, dx \\ &= \int (P_4 - 3)(\sec^4(P_1 + 1)x - \sec^2(P_1 + 1)x) \sec(P_1 + 1)x \tan(P_1 + 1)x \, dx \end{aligned}$$

by substitution:

$$u = \sec(P_1 + 1)x \quad \Rightarrow \quad du = (P_1 + 1) \sec(P_1 + 1)x \tan(P_1 + 1)x \, dx$$

$$\Rightarrow \int (P_4 - 3)(\sec^4(P_1 + 1)x - \sec^2(P_1 + 1)x) \sec(P_1 + 1)x \tan(P_1 + 1)x \, dx$$

$$= \frac{P_4 - 3}{P_1 + 1} \int (u^4 + u^2) \, du$$

$$= \left(-3 + \frac{3}{2}P_1 + \frac{1}{2}P_4\right) \left(\frac{u^3}{3} - \frac{u^5}{5}\right) + C$$

$$= \left(-3 + \frac{3}{2}P_1 + \frac{1}{2}P_4\right) \left(\frac{\sec^3(P_1 + 1)x}{3} - \frac{\sec^5(P_1 + 1)x}{5}\right) + C$$

where:

$C = a_0 + a_1P_1 + a_2P_2 + a_3P_3 + a_4P_4$; a_0, a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4 are real numbers.

and:

$$\frac{P_4 - 3}{P_1 + 1} = x_0 + x_1P_1 + x_2P_2 + x_3P_3 + x_4P_4$$

$$P_4 - 3 = (P_1 + 1)(x_0 + x_1P_1 + x_2P_2 + x_3P_3 + x_4P_4)$$

$$P_4 - 3 = x_0P_1 + x_1P_1 + x_2P_2 + x_3P_3 + x_4P_4 + x_0 + x_1P_1 + x_2P_2 + x_3P_3 + x_4P_4$$

$$P_4 - 3 = x_0 + (x_0 + 2x_1)P_1 + 2x_2P_2 + 2x_3P_3 + 2x_4P_4$$

then:

$$x_0 = -3, x_1 = \frac{3}{2}, x_2 = 0, x_3 = 0 \text{ and } x_4 = \frac{1}{2}$$

hence:

$$\frac{P_4-3}{P_1+1} = -3 + \frac{3}{2}P_1 + \frac{1}{2}P_4$$

III. $\int \cot^m(PN_s x) \csc^n(PN_s x) dx$, where m and n are positive integers.

To find this integral, we can distinguish the following cases:

➤ Case n is even:

- split of $\csc^2(PN_s x)$
- apply $\csc^2(PN_s x) = 1 + \cot^2(PN_s x)$
- we substitution $u = \cot(PN_s x)$

➤ Case m is odd:

- split of $\csc(PN_s x) \cot(PN_s x)$
- apply $\cot^2(PN_s x) = \csc^2(PN_s x) - 1$
- we substitution $u = \csc(PN_s x)$

➤ Case m even and n odd:

- apply $\cot^2(PN_s x) = \csc^2(PN_s x) - 1$
- we substitution $u = \csc(PN_s x)$ or $u = \cot(PN_s x)$, depending on the case.

Example 6

$$\text{Find: } \int 2P_9 \sqrt{\cot(P_8 x)} \csc^4(P_8 x) dx$$

Solution:

$$n = 4 \text{ (even)}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \int 2P_9 \sqrt{\cot(P_8 x)} \csc^4(P_8 x) dx &= \int 2P_9 \cot^{1/2}(P_8 x) \csc^2(P_8 x) \csc^2(P_8 x) dx \\ &= \int 2P_9 (\cot^{1/2}(P_8 x) + \cot^{3/2}(P_8 x)) \csc^2(P_8 x) dx \end{aligned}$$

by substitution:

$$\begin{aligned} u = \cot(P_8 x) &\quad \Rightarrow \quad du = -P_8 \csc^2(P_8 x) dx \\ &\Rightarrow \int 2P_9 \left(\cot^{1/2}(P_8 x) + \cot^{3/2}(P_8 x) \right) \csc^2(P_8 x) dx \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= -\frac{2P_9}{P_8} \int (u^{1/2} + u^{3/2}) du \\
&= -(x_0 + x_1P_1 + x_2P_2 + x_3P_3 + x_4P_4 + x_5P_5 + x_6P_6 + x_7P_7 + x_8P_8 + 2P_9) \left(\frac{2}{3} u^{\frac{3}{2}} + \frac{2}{5} u^{\frac{5}{2}} \right) + C \\
&= (x_0 + x_1P_1 + x_2P_2 + x_3P_3 + x_4P_4 + x_5P_5 + x_6P_6 + x_7P_7 + x_8P_8 + 2P_9) \left(-\frac{2}{3} \cot^{\frac{3}{2}}(P_8x) \right. \\
&\quad \left. - \frac{2}{5} \cot^{5/2}(P_8x) \right) + C
\end{aligned}$$

where:

$$\begin{aligned}
C &= a_0 + a_1P_1 + a_2P_2 + a_3P_3 + a_4P_4 + a_5P_5 + a_6P_6 + a_7P_7 + a_8P_8 + a_9P_9 \\
&; \quad a_0, a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4, a_5, a_6, a_7, a_8, a_9 \text{ are real numbers.}
\end{aligned}$$

and:

$$\frac{2P_9}{P_8} = x_0 + x_1P_1 + x_2P_2 + x_3P_3 + x_4P_4 + x_5P_5 + x_6P_6 + x_7P_7 + x_8P_8 + x_9P_9$$

$$2P_9 = (P_8)(x_0 + x_1P_1 + x_2P_2 + x_3P_3 + x_4P_4 + x_5P_5 + x_6P_6 + x_7P_7 + x_8P_8 + x_9P_9)$$

$$2P_9 = x_0P_8 + x_1P_8 + x_2P_8 + x_3P_8 + x_4P_8 + x_5P_8 + x_6P_8 + x_7P_8 + x_8P_8 + x_9P_9$$

$$2P_9 = (x_0 + x_1 + x_2 + x_3 + x_4 + x_5 + x_6 + x_7 + x_8)P_8 + x_9P_9$$

then:

$$x_0 + x_1 + x_2 + x_3 + x_4 + x_5 + x_6 + x_7 + x_8 = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad x_9 = 2$$

hence:

$$\frac{2P_9}{P_8} = x_0 + x_1P_1 + x_2P_2 + x_3P_3 + x_4P_4 + x_5P_5 + x_6P_6 + x_7P_7 + x_8P_8 + 2P_9$$

$$\text{where: } x_0 + x_1 + x_2 + x_3 + x_4 + x_5 + x_6 + x_7 + x_8 = 0$$

Plithogenic trigonometric identities:

$$1) \quad \sin(PN_r x) \cos(PN_s x) = \frac{1}{2} [\sin(PN_r + PN_s)x + \sin(PN_r - PN_s)x]$$

$$2) \quad \cos(PN_r x) \sin(PN_s x) = \frac{1}{2} [\sin(PN_r + PN_s)x - \sin(PN_r - PN_s)x]$$

$$3) \quad \cos(PN_r x) \cos(PN_s x) = \frac{1}{2} [\cos(PN_r + PN_s)x + \cos(PN_r - PN_s)x]$$

$$4) \quad \sin(PN_r x) \sin(PN_s x) = \frac{-1}{2} [\cos(PN_r + PN_s)x - \cos(PN_r - PN_s)x]$$

Example 7

Find:

$$\begin{aligned}
 1) \int P_3 \sin(P_2 + 3)x \cos(2P_1 - 1)x \, dx &= \int \frac{1}{2} P_3 [\sin(P_2 + 2P_1 + 2)x + \sin(P_2 - 2P_1 + 4)x] \, dx \\
 &= \frac{1}{2} \left[-\left(\frac{P_3}{P_2 + 2P_1 + 2}\right) \cos(P_2 + 2P_1 + 2)x - \left(\frac{P_3}{P_2 - 2P_1 + 4}\right) \cos(P_2 - 2P_1 + 4)x \right] + C \\
 &= \frac{1}{2} \left[-\frac{1}{5} P_3 \cos(P_2 + 2P_1 + 2)x - \frac{1}{3} P_3 \cos(P_2 - 2P_1 + 4)x \right] + C \\
 &= -\frac{1}{10} P_3 \cos(P_2 + 2P_1 + 2)x - \frac{1}{6} P_3 \cos(P_2 - 2P_1 + 4)x + C
 \end{aligned}$$

where:

$$C = a_0 + a_1 P_1 + a_2 P_2 + a_3 P_3 ; \quad a_0, a_1, a_2, a_3 \text{ are real numbers.}$$

and:

$$\frac{P_3}{P_2 + 2P_1 + 2} = x_0 + x_1 P_1 + x_2 P_2 + x_3 P_3$$

$$P_3 = (P_2 + 2P_1 + 2)(x_0 + x_1 P_1 + x_2 P_2 + x_3 P_3 + x_0 + x_1 P_1 + x_2 P_2 + x_3 P_3 + x_0 + x_1 P_1 + x_2 P_2 + x_3 P_3)$$

$$P_3 = 2x_0 + 2x_1 P_1 + 2x_2 P_2 + 2x_3 P_3 + 2x_0 P_1 + 2x_1 P_1 + 2x_2 P_2 + 2x_3 P_3 + x_0 P_2 + x_1 P_2 + x_2 P_2 + x_3 P_3$$

$$P_3 = 2x_0 + (2x_0 + 4x_1)P_1 + (x_0 + x_1 + 5x_2)P_2 + 5x_3 P_3$$

then:

$$x_0 = 0 , \quad x_1 = 0 , \quad x_2 = 0 , \quad x_3 = \frac{1}{5}$$

hence:

$$\frac{P_3}{P_2 + 2P_1 + 3} = \frac{1}{5} P_3$$

and we have:

$$\frac{P_3}{P_2 - 2P_1 + 4} = x_0 + x_1 P_1 + x_2 P_2 + x_3 P_3$$

$$P_3 = (P_2 - 2P_1 + 4)(x_0 + x_1 P_1 + x_2 P_2 + x_3 P_3 + x_0 + x_1 P_1 + x_2 P_2 + x_3 P_3 + x_0 + x_1 P_1 + x_2 P_2 + x_3 P_3)$$

$$P_3 = 4x_0 + 4x_1 P_1 + 4x_2 P_2 + 4x_3 P_3 - 2x_0 P_1 - 2x_1 P_1 - 2x_2 P_2 - 2x_3 P_3 + x_0 P_2 + x_1 P_2 + x_2 P_2 + x_3 P_3$$

$$P_3 = 4x_0 + (-2x_0 + 2x_1)P_1 + (x_0 + x_1 + 3x_2)P_2 + 3x_3 P_3$$

then:

$$x_0 = 0 , \quad x_1 = 0 , \quad x_2 = 0 , \quad x_3 = \frac{1}{3}$$

hence:

$$\frac{P_3}{P_2 - 2P_1 + 4} = \frac{1}{3} P_3$$

$$2) \int P_2 \cos(P_2 x) \cos(2P_2 x) \, dx = \int \frac{1}{2} P_2 [\cos(3P_2 x) + \cos(P_2 x)] \, dx$$

$$= \frac{1}{2} [(x_0 + x_1 P_1 + x_2 P_2) \sin(3P_2 x) + (x_0 + x_1 P_1 + x_2 P_2) \sin(P_2 x)] + C$$

where:

$C = a_0 + a_1 P_1 + a_2 P_2$; a_0, a_1, a_2 are real numbers.

and:

$$\frac{P_2}{3P_2} = x_0 + x_1 P_1 + x_2 P_2$$

$$P_2 = (3P_2)(x_0 + x_1 P_1 + x_2 P_2)$$

$$P_2 = 3x_0 P_2 + 3x_1 P_2 + 3x_2 P_2$$

$$P_2 = (3x_0 + 3x_1 + 3x_2)P_2$$

then:

$$x_0 + x_1 + x_2 = \frac{1}{3}$$

hence:

$$\frac{P_2}{3P_2} = x_0 + x_1 P_1 + x_2 P_2, \text{ where: } x_0 + x_1 + x_2 = \frac{1}{3}$$

and we have:

$$\frac{P_2}{P_2} = \acute{x}_0 + \acute{x}_1 P_1 + \acute{x}_2 P_2$$

$$P_2 = (P_2)(\acute{x}_0 + \acute{x}_1 P_1 + \acute{x}_2 P_2)$$

$$P_2 = \acute{x}_0 P_2 + \acute{x}_1 P_2 + \acute{x}_2 P_2$$

$$P_2 = (\acute{x}_0 + \acute{x}_1 + \acute{x}_2)P_2$$

then:

$$\acute{x}_0 + \acute{x}_1 + \acute{x}_2 = 1$$

hence:

$$\frac{P_2}{P_2} = \acute{x}_0 + \acute{x}_1 P_1 + \acute{x}_2 P_2, \text{ where: } \acute{x}_0 + \acute{x}_1 + \acute{x}_2 = 1$$

$$3) \int P_4 \sin(P_7 + 3)x \sin(P_6 - 3)x \, dx = \int \frac{-1}{2} P_4 [\cos(P_7 + P_6 + 6)x - \cos(P_7 - P_6)x] \, dx$$

= dose not exist

because:

$$\frac{P_4}{P_7 + P_6 + 6} = (\text{dose not exist})$$

$$\text{and } \frac{P_4}{P_7 - P_6} = (\text{dose not exist})$$

5. Conclusions

In this paper, we studied the indefinite plithogenic trigonometric integrals by presenting integration methods specific to the plithogenic field; we concluded that we could obtain an integration that does not exist in the plithogenic field, as the division process is not possible according to the concept presented by Smarandache.

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